

Microdetermination of palladium(II) using 5-chloro-8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline as a complexing agent

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Abstract : A simple, rapid, highly selective and sensitive method for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) in trace amounts is worked out employing 5-chloro-8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline as a complexing agent for the metal ion and extracting the coloured complex into chloroform from 1 M H₂SO₄ solution, whose absorbance is measured at 450 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0–2.6 µg Pd^{II} mL⁻¹. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex are 0.9×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0119 µg Pd cm⁻², respectively. The method is free from the interference of a large number of elements including molybdenum, tungsten, tantalum, silver and other platinum metals. The proposed method handles satisfactorily the analysis of several samples of varying complexity.

Keywords : Palladium, 5-chloro-8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline, extractive spectrophotometry.

Introduction

It has been observed that in a wide variety of samples¹, palladium is generally present in very low concentrations. This fact calls for laying out better methods of trace determination, based on specific and sensitive reactions of the metal ion, which will go a long way towards its enrichment and use as a catalyst. It is evident from the survey of literature that the existing methods of spectrophotometric determination of palladium using various complexing agents are generally time consuming, lacking both in sensitivity and selectivity and have limited applications at times due to cumbersome procedures².

An attempt has, therefore, been made to develop a simple spectrophotometric method for microdetermination of palladium(II) using 5-chloro-8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline as a complexing agent in acid medium. Effects of different parameters on the proposed method of determination have been studied in detail.

Experimental

A UV-Vis spectrophotometer (140-02 Shimadzu, Japan) with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used. A stock solution of (1 mg mL⁻¹) of palladium was obtained by dissolving 0.167 g of PdCl₂ (Sisco) in a minimum volume of HCl and standardized gravimetrically³. Working solutions of the metal ion (µg mL⁻¹) were obtained by suitable dilutions therefrom. Similarly, solutions of other

metal ions were prepared from their commonly available salts and solution of anions were obtained by dissolving sodium or potassium salts in deionised water. Chloroform employed for extraction, was of A.R. variety. The reagent 5-chloro-8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline (CHI), 0.1% (m/v) was prepared in ethanol.

Reagent : 5-Chloro-8 hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of palladium and other metal ions in suitable proportions, as shown in Table 1.

Pd-charcoal catalyst (Aldrich 20, 568-0) : The sample (0.05 g) was dissolved in a minimum volume of aqua regia by heating. The charcoal was filtered off when hot. Nitric acid was destroyed completely by evaporating the solution to dryness. The residue thus obtained was dissolved in water, filtered and the filtrate was processed for the determination of palladium as described below in the procedure.

Procedure : To the sample solution containing 20 µg

Table 1. Analysis of various samples with the proposed method

Sl. no.	Sample composition Matrix*	Pd added (μg)	Pd found** (μg)
1.	Zr (0.05), Mg (2), Be (2) ^a	20	19.4
2.	Fe (0.10), Cd (5), Nb (0.10) ^b	22	22.6
3.	Ru (0.100), Rh (0.050)	18	18.6
4.	W (0.5), Hg (2), Mn (2)	24	24.6
5.	U (1), Zn (2), Cr (1)	15	15.8
6.	Mo (0.010), As (0.1), Th (0.050)	25	25.3
7.	Ni (0.060), Pt (0.050), V (0.050)***	5	4.9
8.	Au (0.08)***	20	20
9.	Ag (0.028), Co (0.002)***	10	10.5
10.	Au (0.09)***	10	10.5
11.	Pd-charcoal catalyst	5%	5.2

*Amount of metal ion shown in parentheses is in mg, **average of triplicate analyses, ***composition of samples 7, 8, 9, 10 corresponds to Palau, Palau, Palladium gold, white gold, ^ain presence of 40 mg phosphate, ^bin presence of 40 mg ascorbic acid.

Pd and/or other ions in a 100 mL separating funnel were added 0.5 mL H_2SO_4 (1 M) and 1 ml reagent, CHI (0.1% m/v) and the volume was made upto 10 mL with deionised water. The contents were gently mixed and equilibrated once with an equal volume of chloroform for 30 s. The two phases were allowed to separate and the organic layer was filtered through a Whatman's filter paper. no. 41 into a 10 mL volumetric flask, which was filled upto the mark with pure chloroform. The contents were gently mixed and the absorbance of the yellow colored species was measured at 450 nm against pure chloroform using 1 cm quartz cells. The amount of the metal ion was determined from the standard curve drawn by plotting a graph between μg amounts of Pd^{II} and the corresponding absorbance values following the above procedure.

Results and discussion

In acid solution, Pd^{II} forms a yellow colored complex with the reagent CHI, which is extractable into chloroform. The effect of different acids on the absorbance of the Pd^{II} complex (in chloroform) was studied at 1 N for all the acids and it was found that the absorbance of the complex decreases in the order : $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{HCl} > \text{CH}_3\text{COOH} > \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$. Therefore, H_2SO_4 was considered suitable for the system.

Various organic solvents have been tried as extractants for the metal complex. The extraction behaviour in terms of absorbance was found to decrease in the order : chloroform > 1,2-dichloroethane > benzene > carbon tetra-

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectrum of Pd^{II} -CHI complex : A (■) Absorbance of palladium complex measured against blank, B (▲) Absorbance of reagent blank measured against pure chloroform.

chloride > dichloromethane > ethyl acetate > toluene > isobutylmethyl ketone > ethylacetate > amyl acetate > isoamyl alcohol > cyclohexane. As chloroform gives maximum absorbance with a rapid and clear phase separation, it was chosen as an extractant for the complex. A single equilibration of the aqueous phase with an equal volume (10 mL) of chloroform, under optimum conditions of the procedure, gave quantitative (100%) extraction of the metal complex.

The absorption spectrum of the complex in chloroform shows maximum at 445–460 nm, where the reagent blank hardly shows any absorbance. The coloured Pd^{II} -CHI complex was stable for more than 8 h in chloroform at 450 nm. The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were 0.3–1.0 mL of 1 M H_2SO_4 , 0.8–1.3 mL of CHI (0.1% in ethanol), and 15–180 s equilibration time for $\leq 26 \mu\text{g}$ Pd^{II} per 10 mL aqueous volume.

Beer's law was valid in the palladium concentration range of 0–2.6 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. However, the optimum range of determination of palladium as evaluated from Ringbom plot was found to be 0.8–2.2 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 450 nm are $0.9 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0119 \mu\text{g Pd cm}^{-2}$,

respectively. The metal to ligand ratio in the complex has been determined as 1 : 2 by applying Job's method of continuous variations and the same is further confirmed by the mole ratio method³.

The effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the procedure containing 20 µg Pd^{II} in 10 ml of aqueous volume, the effects of anions added as their sodium or potassium salts have been studied. Several anions like chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, acetate, tartrate, phosphate, citrate, sulfosalicylic acid, 50 mg each; ascorbic acid, 40 mg; fluoride, 30 mg; oxalate, 5 mg; thiourea, 0.05 mg; are without effect. However, EDTA and nitrate show interference. Amongst the cations, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Mg^{II}, Hg^{II}, Sr^{II}, 10 mg each; Co^{II}, Ta^V, As^V, Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, Be^{II}, Cd^{II}, W^{VI}, 5 mg each; U^{VI}, 4 mg; Os^{VIII}, 2.9 mg; Ca^{II}, Au^{III}, Ag^I, Nb^V, Se^{IV}, Ti^{IV}, 1 mg each; Bi^{III}, 0.8 mg; Th^{IV}, Sb^{III}, Sn^{II}, 0.5 mg each; Re^{VII}, 0.3 mg; Ru^{III}, Cr^{VI}, 0.2 mg each; Ti^{IV}, Ir^{III}, 0.1 mg each; Pt^{II}, 0.05 mg; V^V, Mo^{VI}, 0.02 mg each; do not show any absorbance. The interference due to Zr^{IV} and Fe^{II,III} can be eliminated by using phosphate and ascorbic acid as masking agents, respectively. The presence of Cu^{II} increases absorbance of the complex and thus interferes.

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